

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF GYPSUM PLASTERBOARD MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR IN THREE POINTS BENDING TESTS.

F. Hernández-Olivares, F. Lasheras, M. del Rio, E. Rodríguez and L. de Villanueva.

Departamento de Construcción y Tecnología Arquitectónicas. E.T.S. de Arquitectura. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Avda. Juan de Herrera, 4. 28040 Madrid. España.

ABSTRACT

A mathematical model to obtain the breaking strength in three points bending tests of Gypsum Plasterboard from its geometrical dimensions and mechanical properties of constitutive materials is presented. These predictive values are compared with those proposed by European Community and American Standards, and with laboratory tests. In every case, an excellent agreement between the model predictions and numerical data there exists.

Keywords: Gypsum, board, sandwich, paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that a sandwich is a plate composed by an inner element, the core, between two well bonded peels of a given thickness. The main function of exterior peels is to resist the tensile stress, when it happens, and to protect the core, which mainly contributes to the sandwich stiffness, low density and shear strength (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Gypsum board sandwich panel.

Gypsum board panels are widely used in building applications. They are composed by a gypsum core with faces bonded to multi-ply external paper laminates. Small quantities of some additives are mixed with the plaster before and during the setting: starch and other products get the core better performance, and excellent linkage between core and paper peels.

Gypsum board paper is multi-ply or laminate primarily made from recycled paper fiber (5 to 9 plies). The inner plies in the sandwich configuration are sized with silicone and the outer ones with some resin. The silicone sizing lets the porosity between paper fibers open. So, the inner plies retain the setting water and gypsum particles can introduce into open porosity, getting excellent bonding between paper and gypsum, without starch loss, which could promote damage in drying by local stratification near from interfaces¹.

After this process and setting, Gypsum board paper tensile strength and Young modules are greater than those of Gypsum. So, Gypsum board plates have the main characteristics of a sandwich element².

2. OBJECTIVES

The objective of this work has been to design a mathematical model of the mechanical behavior of Gypsum board plates in bending tests, to obtain a formula for the plate breaking load in function of test characteristics, materials properties and geometrical dimensions of the sandwich plate.

Two reasons made to us this model necessary. The first one of scientific nature: to learn about the plates mechanical properties controlling mechanisms. The second one: the in force or as project local and international Standard and Codes (UNE, BS, ISO, CEN Project, ASTM)³ establish for breaking load in three points bending tests some demand able minimum values, depending on laboratory conditions (moisture content) and samples geometry.

These numerical values have been obtained from a lot of experimental tests, but there is no agreement between those proposed by different countries and international organizations, mainly due to the absence of a rational and universally accepted pattern.

So, a simple mathematical formula based on an simple model for Gypsum board plates, can contribute to make easy the adoption of internationally acceptable criteria on minimum mechanical strength for plates.

3. METHODOLOGY

At first, the basic architecture of plates is established, jointly with the physical and mechanical properties measurements of constitutive materials. In second place, a mathematical model of plates mechanical behavior under three points bending tests is adopted⁴. From this model, a simple mathematical formula for the breaking load is obtained.

To verify this formula, a lot of laboratory tests was accomplished. The loads obtained are compared both, with those proposed by Standards and those derived from the mathematical model, having into account the material properties of sandwich constitutive elements experimentally determined.

4. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

To describe the mechanical behavior of Gypsum board plates in three points bending tests a mathematical model based on transformed section theory is proposed.

The following procedure is used in the determination of transformed section properties: 1) A plate of given length, width and thickness is selected. 2) A reference elastic modules E_r is chosen: that of the paper cover under tensile stress, E_c , for instance. 3) The modular ratio n is determined for each element i of the cross-section:

$$n_i = \frac{E_i}{E_r} = \frac{E_i}{E_c}$$

4) The actual width of each element of the cross-section is multiplied for the modular ratio, to obtain the transformed width. The new cross-section is the transformed section.

Then, the elementary theory of bending in beams of variable section is applied. According to this theory, the maximum load in three points bending tests is given by

$$P = \frac{2Z\sigma_c}{s} \quad (1)$$

where: P is the applied load; Z, section modulus in bending; σ_c , tensile strength of paper cover; s, distance between cylindrical supports in test machine.

In eq. 1 a fracture criterion is assumed, $\sigma_{\max} = \sigma_c$, σ_{\max} been the maximum tensile stress in section, that of the outer extreme fiber of beam. The similarity between two paper lamina covers allows to accept that the neutral axis coincide with symmetry axis.

The transformed section modulus Z can be calculated using

$$Z = \frac{2 I}{h}$$

where I is the transformed section inertia, and h the gypsum board thickness.

Fig. 2. Real and transformed section geometry

According to real and transformed section geometry's (Fig. 2), the following expression for I is obtained:

$$I = \frac{wth^2}{2} + \frac{nwh^3}{12} \quad (2)$$

where the approximation of paper cover thickness $t \ll h$ has been included, and w being sandwich width (Fig. 2).

So, the section modulus is given by:

$$Z = wth + \frac{nh^2}{6} \quad (3)$$

In such a way that

$$P = \sigma_c \frac{2 wth}{\sigma} \left(1 + \frac{nh}{6 t} \right) \quad (4)$$

5. EXPERIMENTAL

Gypsum board panels tested in laboratory have been supplied by EPYSA, in three different thicknesses: 9.5, 12.5, and 15 mm. Three sets of panels with different width (200, 300 and 400 mm) have been selected for testing under several values of distance between cylindrical supports (span: 250, 350 and 450 mm).

Specimens width and length do not coincide in some case with those proposed in ISO 6308 and ASTM (C 36-80) Standard, because testing main purpose has been to verify mathematical formula (eq. 4) just derived.

To determine mechanical properties of Gypsum plaster core, 18 samples of this material have been taken from the same batch, in Gypsum wallboard manufacturing continuum process, of tested panels. These specimens (40x40x160 mm) have been tested in bending and compression, obtaining Gypsum rupture modules, flexural strength and Young modules.

Mechanical properties of paper lamina -Young modules and tensile strength- have been experimentally measured too, in tensile tests of specimens obtained from same big roller which Gypsum board panels were made.

Fig. 4.- Relation between theoretical and experimental minimum breaking loads (plates 9,5 mm thick). $P_{exp} = 1,05P_{th} - 18,6$ (N).

Figs. 4, 5 and 6 collect experimental values of minimum breaking loads relative to theoretical ones, for plates thicknesses 9.5, 12.5 and 15 mm, respectively, and for different values of specimens width and span.

Fig. 5.- Relation between theoretical and experimental minimum breaking loads (plates 12,5 mm thick). $P_{exp} = 0,95P_{th} - 78,6$ (N).

Fig. 6.- Relation between theoretical and experimental minimum breaking loads (plates 15 mm thick). $P_{exp} = 0,84P_{th} - 122,7$ (N).

6. DISCUSSION

Theoretical values predicted by mathematical model are in close agreement with experimental ones, for three points bending tests, accomplished according to Standard Regulations in order to verify Gypsum board minimum mechanical strength.

This mathematical formula (eq. 4) can be used as reference to assess the final product quality, and to modify, if necessary, those variables altering the desired plates performance.

The theoretical breaking load is obtained from geometrical data (span, width, and thickness) and mechanical properties of constitutive materials: paper cover and plaster. The first data set can not be altered: in eq. 4 those exact values measured in testing are introduced.

Nevertheless, some variations on mechanical properties of constitutive materials are likely happening in plates manufacturing process. It has not been able to separate paper cover from plaster core, without severe damage in both. So, experimentally measured values of Gypsum and paper Young modules, and paper tensile stress, can be lightly different of those same materials in sandwich configuration, under hygrothermal and mechanical agents.

Likewise, setting and drying of gypsum core and drying of paper cover are occurring in manufacturing process, in different conditions as similar setting and drying of prismatic gypsum specimens in well controlled laboratory moisture room and drying oven.

These reasons explain small differences between some theoretical values, mainly those of thick specimens, and experimental ones, and it can be said that the particular manufacturing process analyzed is excellent, because mathematical model gives the better attainable (upper bounds) breaking loads.

A bias seems to be, nevertheless, towards experimentally measured breaking load smaller than those predicted by eq. 4, which can be analyzed discussing the minimum values for breaking load established by Standard Regulations.

Fig. 7. Minimum breaking loads in European Standards

Minimum breaking loads in Spanish Standard, ISO and CEN Project, are collected in fig. 7, for specimens of different thickness and constant length x width (400 x 300 mm), tested under longitudinal fiber direction conditions, and fixed distance between cylindrical supports in text machine (350 mm).

Only in CEN Project plates of thickness greater than 18 mm are considered, having a minimum breaking load proportional to thickness, with smaller slope than those accepted by Standard Regulations above quoted, on samples with thickness smaller than 18 mm.

Nevertheless, ASTM Regulation (fig. 8) adopts linear relations for minimum breaking load vs. thickness, for longitudinal and transversal tests.

Fig. 8.- Minimum ASTM breaking load

ASTM specimens sizes (405 x 305 x h mm) are different from European Regulations ones. Distance between parallels support in test machine is different too (356 mm in ASTM). So, it is not possible to compare directly ASTM and European breaking load values.

Fig. 9 collects experimental results of minimum breaking load of six specimen sets tested in bending (longitudinal and transversal conditions), according to Spanish Standard Regulations (specimen size, span, load rate, laboratory moisture conditions, etc.). Lines of different thickness represent minimum breaking loads in European Regulation. The material behaviour is quite acceptable.

The excellent agreement between minimum breaking load values and theoretical ones allows to suggest the inclusion of eq. 4 in Standard Regulations besides the lot of not well justified numerical values.

That formula explains too the conversion factor f,

$$f = \frac{400 \times 350}{300 \times s} = \frac{466,7}{s} \quad (5)$$

appearing in some Standard (ISO, CEN Project), to determine the breaking load of gypsum plasterboard when specimens with constant slenderness ratio (span:thickness) of 40:1 and sample width of 400 mm. Eq. 5 is actually straightforward derived from eq. 4.

Fig. 9.- Comparison between experimental and Standard breaking loads in European Regulations.

Finally, due to eq. 4 a linear -or piecewise linear- relation between thickness and breaking load implies that gypsum/paper Young modules ratio n depends on plasterboard thickness, which means that is been influenced by manufacturing process, as was mentioned above.

The minimum tensile strength of paper cover in Standard is 220 N in longitudinal direction and 65 N in transversal direction (15 mm paper specimen width), which implies following relations between Young modules ratio n and thickness h (in mm), and data collected from European Standards:

$$n_{LONG} = \frac{1,40}{h}$$

$$n_{TRANS} = \frac{2,15}{h}$$

Certainly, ASTM values give similar relations. Nevertheless, two critical thickness values (14 mm in transverse direction and 19 mm in longitudinal one) are obtained assuming n exponential decay with growing h , from ASTM minimum breaking loads.

Gypsum core stiffness dependence on plate thickness is also evident in Shore C measurements:

	<u>Shore C</u>
Gypsum prismatic beams (40x40x160 mm)	62
Gypsum board core (9,5 mm thick)	60
Gypsum board core (12,5 mm thick)	54
Gypsum board core (15 mm thick)	53

7. CONCLUSIONS

1. A mathematical model of mechanical behaviour of Gypsum board panels in three points bending tests has been developed. It is based on transformed section theory of sandwich panels, and gives minimum breaking load for gypsum board as function of specimen size, paper cover thickness, span and materials properties.

2. Experimental laboratory tests confirm the model soundness, for plates thickness of 9.5, 12.5 and 15 mm, at least. Nevertheless, some plates 15 mm thick show smaller minimum breaking load than predicted. This suggests some influence in material properties from manufacturing process, altering Young modules ratio n , as Shore C measurements confirm.

3. Minimum breaking loads established in European Standard and ASTM linearly depend on panels thickness, which implies -by examining eq. 4, just derived- that inherently are accepted non optimum stiffness in plates with thickness greater than 15 mm.

4. Mathematical formula obtained (eq. 4) must be included in actual Regulations, in such a way that minimum breaking loads there proposed could be compared with similar values obtained through scientific and more comprehensive arguments. The famous conversion factor f can get better acceptance, on these theoretical grounds.

Acknowledgments

This research has been accomplished under Contract for Scientific and Technical Cooperation between "Española de Placas de Yeso S.A." (EPYSA) and "Departamento de Construcción y Tecnología Arquitectónica. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid", and received financial support from that Contract.

The EPYSA R&D Department has greatly contributed supplying technical reports, material and valuable discussions. The authors also wish to express thanks to this Department for his permission to publish this results and discussions.

Finally, the authors thank to Mr. F. Egido his work in the realization of laboratory tests.

References

- 1 Metzler.R.B. "Sizing Gypsum board Paper with Silicone". Gypsum board Conference. Buenos Aires. 1976.
- 2 Allen.H.G. "Analysis of Structural Sandwich Panels". Pergamon Press. 1969.
- 3 BS 1230. British Standard Institution. 1975
DRAFT Proposal for CEN Standard, "Gypsum Plasterboard Specification- Test Methods. June 1989.
ISO 6308. "Gypsum Plasterboard -Specification- 1st. Ed. 1980-11-01.
ASTM C 473-81. "Standard Methods for Physical Testing of Gypsum Board Products, Gypsum Lath, Gypsum Partítion, Gypsum Slabs". C 36-80. "Standard Specification for Gypsum Wallboard". Ed. American Society for Testing and Materials. 1983.
- 4 Chambers.R.E. "Flat Sandwich Structures", in Structural Plastics Design Manual, Ch. 8. ASCE Manuals and Reports on Engineering Practice No. 63. 1984